

The Impact of International Integration on the Sustainable Trade Development in Vietnam

Author's Details: ⁽¹⁾Van Su Ha-Thuongmai university, Hanoi, Vietnam

⁽²⁾Nguyen Dieu Anh Le-University of Economics – Technology for Industries, Hanoi, Vietnam

Correspondence: Nguyen Dieu Anh Le, 456 Minh Khai, Hai Ba Trung, Ha Noi, Vietnam.

Abstract:

The objective of this paper is to assess the factors affecting the sustainable trade development of Bac Ninh Province, Vietnam. We conducted data analysis on 338 commercial enterprises in Bac Ninh province. The results show that international integration is the most important factor affecting the sustainable trade development of Bac Ninh province. Besides, the factor of natural conditions is the one that has the least impact on the sustainable trade development of Bac Ninh province. From there, we make recommendations to help Bac Ninh Province improve the efficiency of sustainable trade development.

Keywords: Sustainable trade development, international integration, Bac Ninh, Vietnam

1. Introduction

Implementing proactively and actively international integration, in recent years, the process of international integration of Vietnam has reached a new level. The process of international integration has made an important contribution to raising the position and power of Vietnam in socio-economic development and raising incomes for people; create pressure and conditions to actively improve economic institutions; efforts to improve national competitiveness, businesses and products ... However, the integration process also brings many challenges to the process of socio-economic development of Vietnam.

Sustainable development is an indispensable trend in the development process of society, is a strategic choice, including economic changes, as well as social, cultural and educational changes. , science and technology, about the environment and human development. Sustainable development is an indispensable need and is a challenge for all countries, industries and localities in the context of globalization and international economic integration, especially for developing countries implementing the later industrialized like Vietnam. To ensure that Sustainable Development requires Sustainable Development in all areas, in which trade is an important area that creates that sustainability. In terms of international integration, trade is particularly important; trade is both an integral part of the national economy and an economic lever to promote economic development. Great impact on socio-economic development. In recent years, the issue of Sustainable Development in general and sustainable trade development in particular has been a hot topic in most economic and social forums from research discussion to agenda. This is also the central issue throughout the Vietnam trade development strategy for the period 2011-2020 and subsequent years.

Bac Ninh is a city bordering Hanoi capital of Vietnam, in recent years Bac Ninh province has made very strong moves in the rising economy as one of the provinces with the largest GDP in the country. In order to achieve such results, commercialization development is a prerequisite for economic development.

The paper analyzes the factors affecting the sustainable trade development of Bac Ninh province. The structure of the article in addition to the introduction includes: Research overview, research methods, research results and conclusions.

2. Literature review

2.1. Sustainable trade development

Trade policy can have a broad impact on economy, employment, labor standards, social cohesion and the environment.

Trade means business, or more specifically, it is the activity of exchanging - buying and selling goods and services on the market for profit. Entities participating in the market are buyers and sellers, as required by law. If entities in a country have a business relationship with goods or services with foreign partners, this is called international trade.

Trade includes many different activities, mainly: trading and buying and selling goods and services on the market, such as: trading in goods, trading in services, investment, and intellectual property.

Trade development is an increase in all aspects of trade activities, reflected in the increase in quantity - scale, speed; movement in the structure of trade in goods and services and improvement of the quality of trade in the process of exchanging and trading goods and services (trade in goods, trade in services, investment, and intellectual property). The ultimate goal of trade development is to continuously increase the benefits from commercial activities.

Accordingly, sustainable trade development is high (rational), stable, long-term growth in terms of scale and speed of trade activities associated with structural and advanced quality of trade in goods and services. Trade development ensures a harmonious and rational combination between economic, social, environmental and security aspects.

Thus, the implications of sustainable trade development include:

+ Sustainable trade development must have high or reasonable growth (stability), stability, and long-term scale and speed of trade in goods and services. The results of the growth of trade in goods and services have contributed positively to sustainable economic development, affecting the restructuring of the economy in a positive, modern, advanced-developed manner. developing sectors and fields with high added value, employing high quality labor, creating high added value.

Trade development inevitably requires the use of material resources (capital, labor, natural resources, science and technology) and non-material resources (tradition, history, culture, etc.). ensure that the current use of resources for trade development does not impede or affect the future generations' use of resources for trade development.

In international trade, the manifestation of sustainable trade development, on the one hand, is shown in the balance of international trade ensuring the balance between export and import, not only leading to trade deficit but also trade in goods and services, investment, intellectual property, ... gaining more and more foreign currencies, rapidly increasing foreign currency accumulation for the economy, ... On the other hand, international trade must have make a positive contribution to promote the transformation of a broad-based economic growth model (the economy mainly uses traditional elements - raw natural resources, cheap labor without accompanying scientific progress. learning - technology) to depth (economy using technology - high technology, high quality labor associated with progress). Ministry of Science and Technology).

+ Sustainable social development of commerce must be linked to ensuring creation of high value-added employment, professional, modern working conditions, and a secure living environment. At the same time, constantly increasing incomes for workers in commercial activities associated with ensuring social security, reducing poverty through trade in goods and services.

+ Developing environmentally sustainable trade to ensure all goods and services trade activities must be linked with ensuring the preservation of fresh air and solid waste treatment. Especially, trade in goods and services must ensure the thrifty and efficient use of natural resources, preserve the soil and water environment ...; Ensuring community health.

In international trade, import and export activities of developing countries, especially low-level developing countries, must comply with the laws of bilateral and multilateral trade agreements. avoid importing goods, as

machines and equipment forming the technological landfills of developed countries. Or import of poor quality food and consumer goods affecting the health of the community.

In the process of promoting trade in goods and services, developing countries not only focus on ensuring security in importing goods and services for production and consumption but also need to pay attention to ensure national security and defense.

Commercial sustainable economic development is very important and is a necessary condition for sustainable trade development in society, environment, and national security. Because commercially sustainable economic development will create existing physical resources to address issues of economic, social, environmental and national security.

2.2. The role of sustainable trade development

- Sustainable trade development contributes to promoting a rational, continuous, stable and long-term economic growth.

The nature of commerce is the business of goods and services. Therefore, sustainable trade development will promote efficient trading of goods and services. Through that, activities of exporting and importing goods and services; investment activities; Intellectual property is strengthened, has a positive impact on domestic production, creating more and more goods and services. In particular, the production of quality and value-added goods and services will boost exports. Thereby increasingly creating job openings, increasing incomes, stimulating consumers, promoting growth, sustainable economic development.

- Sustainable trade development contributes to promoting the transformation of economic growth model associated with economic restructuring.

Trade development, especially international trade development, is to promote export, import and investment activities.

Through export activities, receiving direct investment of countries importing goods and services, especially modern machinery and equipment; advanced services from abroad have contributed to the renovation of outdated economic growth model, mainly using outdated technology, cheap labor, consuming natural resources, and using public services. advanced technology, high quality labor, saving natural resources ...; improve the quality of economic growth. That is, import and investment activities have directly participated in the process of renewing the nation's economic growth model from width to mainly depth.

Once the country imports goods or services; attract and absorb the efficiency of foreign direct investment; acquiring science and high technology through machinery and equipment, contributing to the renewal of a successful economic growth model is one of the important factors to ensure the economy to take off.

- Sustainable trade development contributes to the development of high quality human resources, job creation, income generation, poverty reduction and social security.

Through effective and sustainable trade activities, the economy will be formed to create quality human resources, proceed to develop high-quality human resources, participate in the production process - It is a decisive factor to improve productivity, product quality, and competitiveness of the economy.

At the same time, sustainable trade development will increasingly create new, high value-added workplaces; Increase income for employees.

As the economy grows in quality, wealth is increasing more and more. The fruits of growth impact the increase of income for workers; create material conditions to solve social problems, sustainably reduce poverty and ensure social security.

- Sustainable trade development contributes to ensuring the thrifty and efficient use of natural resources, the protection of flora and fauna (forests and wildlife) in association with the protection of the ecological environment.

Sustainable trade development is in the context of globalization, international integration, and commercial activities must comply with the laws of the country with international commitments on sustainable development, with restrictions, economically using natural resources, protecting forests, wildlife, protecting vegetation and living environment.

In particular, with the commitment of nations in the Earth Summit to the goal of sustainable development, contributing to economical, efficient use and protection of natural resources. Through bilateral and multilateral commitments in FTAs, especially new generation FTAs, must comply with and ensure the criteria and standards of sustainable trade development, In particular, tracing the origin of industrial, agricultural and export products is one of the mandatory principles that has promoted sustainable trade development in particular and sustainable economic development in general.

In addition, sustainable trade development creates strategic trust in exports and imports between countries, promoting national, regional and international security and order.

2.3. The impact of international integration on trade development in a sustainable manner

The increasing process of trade liberalization on a regional and global scale is having profound impacts on all economic, political, social and environmental fields. Countries around the world are trying to integrate into the international trading system in order to take advantage of opportunities for economic development in general and trade in particular.

Through trade liberalization and international integration, at the macro level, countries and localities can promote comparative advantage, improve competitiveness and economic efficiency through resource allocation. more reasonable and more efficient, expanding market access. At the micro level, trade liberalization has a positive impact on domestic competition and industrialization, primarily by reducing input costs, receiving more advanced technology and management skills, and exporting Exports expanded production scale, positive impact on industrialization and economic growth. However, the economies of countries and localities are dependent on the change of the world market. The increasing uncertainty of the world market makes it difficult for trade to maintain a stable growth. Besides, the pressure of competition is greater.

Trade liberalization and international integration have both positive impacts and negative impacts on the ecological environment. Trade liberalization creates favorable conditions for the dissemination of environmentally friendly goods and technologies, making them more widely applicable, and consumers' incomes being constantly improved so demand for use is improved. environment-friendly goods and services are also increasing, people's awareness of the environment is increasing, promoting better conditions for international cooperation in the field of environmental protection. In addition, trade liberalization encourages countries to exploit more and more science and technology in order to achieve rapid economic growth, increasing the risk of cross-border environmental pollution such as environmental pollution. from the sale of outdated technologies, unsecured goods, hazardous waste ...

Liberalizing trade and international integration, expanding opportunities and allocating more effectively flows of goods, services, capital, technology and information flows, leading to the maintenance and improvement of the growth rate. economic growth, the overall consequence is to create jobs, raise incomes and make an important contribution to poverty reduction and narrow the rich-poor gap. However, trade liberalization and international integration can lead to bankruptcy and unemployment in enterprises with low competitiveness, and the adjustment of industry structure may increase unemployment. career, reduce income. The increasingly

popular social standards in terms of trade liberalization are one of the pressures for businesses to pay more attention to employee benefits.

3. Research method

3.1. Research background

Starting from a province where the economy is mainly based on agricultural production, industrial production facilities, especially modern industry, are almost negligible. Up to now, Bac Ninh province has had 15 concentrated industrial parks: more than 18 small and medium industrial zones, trade village industrial clusters with hundreds of factories with modern production technology that have been operating, Bac Ninh Industry from 19th place in 2004 to 9th position nationwide. The total export turnover reached US \$ 1,250 billion, an average increase of 67.2% / year. Products of the industry not only meet the increasing consumption needs of the domestic market but also increase the volume and categories of exported products, creating a significant source of foreign currency to continue investing in development. The handicraft industry is very developed with many traditional trade villages and is called "The land of hundred occupations", some products have been branded in the domestic and world markets such as fine art wooden furniture (Dong Ky - Tu Son), bronze casting (Dai Bai - Gia Binh) ...

Provincial competitiveness ranks 10th nationwide and one of the top three provinces in the North. Foreign economic activities have been expanded, contributing to promoting the image of Bac Ninh, attracting foreign direct investment ranked 7th in the country, 2nd in the key economic region of the North.

3.2. Research sample

In order to test the research hypotheses, we sent surveys to 600 commercial enterprises across the province. After 3 months we collected 356 questionnaires. After preliminary elimination and data entry, there were 338 valid surveys left to be analyzed.

The research model is as follows:

In order to identify, measure and evaluate the influence of factors affecting sustainable trade development, the study uses a multiple linear regression model among six influencing factors, as follows: after:

$$Y = \beta + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \beta_4 X_4 + \beta_5 X_5 + \beta_6 X_6$$

Y: Dependent variable - Sustainable trade development

X1: The first independent variable International integration

X2: The second independent variable Trade institutions

X3: The third independent variable

X4: The fourth independent variable. Commercial human resources

X5: 5th independent variable Trade infrastructure

X6: 6th independent variable Science and technology in trade

4. Research results

Assessing the reliability of the internal consistency scale - Cronbach's Alpha coefficient

As introduced in the research methodology section, the scales used in this study are based on the scales in the set of criteria for sustainable trade development and factors affecting sustainable trade development in In the

theoretical part, the author has selected up to 47 observed variables that through investigations affect different degrees.

Cronbach’s Alpha coefficients were used first to eliminate inappropriate variables. Variables have a smaller corrected item-total-correlation coefficient

.50 will be eliminated and according to Nunnally Peterson and Slate, the Cronbach’s Alpha coefficient is considered in the following cases:

$0.6 \leq \alpha < 0.7$: Acceptable (in the case of a completely new study or in a research context)

$0.7 \leq \alpha < 0.8$: Acceptable $0.8 \leq \alpha < 0.9$: Good

$0.9 \leq \alpha \leq 1$: Very good

The processing tool is Analyze / Scale / Reliability Analysis in SPSS software

Table 1. Illustration of Cronbach’s Alpha test results for variables

Latent variable	Cronbach’s Alpha	Conclude
Sustainable trade development	0.928	Very good
International integration	0.903	Very good
Commercial institution	0.843	Good
Natural condition	0.856	Good
Commercial human resources	0.848	Good
Commercial infrastructure	0.889	Good
Science and technology in trade	0.868	Good

Source: Extracted from the results of processing survey data)

EFA discovery factor analysis

After analyzing the Cronbach's Alpha reliability coefficient, the scales were further evaluated by the EFA discovery factor analysis method to analyze 47 observations of dependent variables and 6 independent variables. KMO (Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin) to measure the compatibility of survey samples.

Hypothesis H0: Observed variables have no correlation in the population H1: Observed variables have a correlation in the population

Table 2. KMO test results

KMO		0.805
Bartlett’s Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	6256.438
	df	629
	Sig.	.000

The results show that: KMO coefficient is $0.805 > 0.5$ and $\text{Sig} = 0.000 < 0.05$, so it is assumed that the correlation between observed variables is correlated with each other in the whole. The H0 hypothesis is rejected.

The EFA results show that all scales meet the requirements for extracting factors, with variance > 50% and factor weight > .50. The lowest factor weight .589 (scale c28), the highest weight .982 (variable c38) of the human resource variable.

Regression model results

To identify, measure and evaluate the influence of 6 independent variables on the dependent variable Y: (X1) International integration; (X2) Commercial institutions; (X3) Natural conditions; (X4) Commercial human resources; (X5) Commercial infrastructure; (X6) Science and technology in commerce. The regression result obtained the value of R² = 0.582, the value of R² indicates that the independent variables in the model can explain 58.2% of the change of the dependent variable, the remaining 41.8% is due to the influence of the Other variables outside the model.

Table 3. Results of regression analysis

Model Summary ^b					
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.835 ^a	.598	.582	.336	1.460
a. Predictors: (Constant), X6, X3, X4, X5, X2, X1					
b. Dependent Variable: Y					

To test the suitability of the overall regression model, we consider the value of F from ANOVA variance analysis table, value of F = 101,618, value of Sig = 0.000, initially showing the linear regression model Multiples match data sets and can be used. The Durbin-Watson statistical quantity = 1,460 shows no correlation between the residuals, which means that the regression model does not violate the assumption of independence of error.

After using the processing tool Analyze / Rgression / Linear in SPSS software, running the regression function results in the following:

Table 4. Multivariate regression results

The coefficients and variables	The coefficient is not standardized		The coefficient is standardized	t	Statistical significance level
	β	Standard deviation	Beta		
Constant	-.662	.227		3.342	.001
International integration	.568	.041	.568	8.782	.000
Commercial institution	.262	.040	.265	7.286	.000
Natural condition	.069	.032	.093	2.731	.007
Commercial human resources	.088	.031	.095	2.743	.007
Commercial infrastructure	.125	.033	.127	3.607	.000
Science and technology	.283	.042	.294	6.880	.000
R ² = 0.691 F = 100.809 (Sig.F = 0.000)					

$$Y = - .662 + .568X1 + .262X2 + .088X3 + .069X4 + .125X5 + .283X6$$

All the coefficients in the model are positive, which means that all six factors have a positive impact on sustainable trade development. Regarding the influence level of the factors, the analysis results show that the International Integration factor has the greatest impact on sustainable trade development in the period of 2012-2018 with coefficient $\beta_1 = .568$. International integration brings great opportunities and advantages but also challenges and challenges for Bac Ninh province in the process of sustainable development. The least affecting factor is the Natural condition with coefficient $\beta_3 = .069$. Therefore, these are important bases for the leadership of Bac Ninh province to develop development strategies and plans suitable to reality, creating great favorable conditions for enterprises and individual business households. trading businesses in the province improve business efficiency as well as ensure sustainable development of trade in the context of world integration today.

5. Conclusion

Based on the research results in section 4, we make some recommendations for sustainable trade development for Bac Ninh province as follows:

(i) With the Government:

Strengthen directing, developing and organizing the implementation of action programs, strategies, and plans for development of industries, products and territories, ensuring the promotion of the advantages and effective use of all resources of The country aims to successfully implement the objectives of its strategy of rapid and sustainable economic development. Promulgate practical policies to develop sustainable trade in localities in the Northern Midland and Mountainous area, including Bac Ninh. Encourage and create favorable conditions for trade activities in this area to promote efficiency, thereby promoting the important role in leading development activities in the province and improving the quality of life. of the population.

Building a commercial development plan of the Northern midland and mountainous region, accordingly, the sustainable development plan of Bac Ninh is grounded and implemented in accordance with the general development trend.

Adopting policies to adequately support investment in commercial infrastructure in urban and mountainous areas, especially market infrastructure. Measures should be taken to curb inflation, stabilize the macro-economy, and create an enabling environment for sustainable trade development. Directing the inspection of the implementation of laws, international practices, focusing on improving the effectiveness of environmental protection.

Develop mechanisms to ensure close coordination among ministries, agencies, and localities under the Government's unified and consistent guidance on the promulgation and implementation of sustainable trade development strategies.

(ii) With the Ministry of Industry and Trade

Assume the prime responsibility for, and coordinate with ministries, branches, localities and industry associations in, elaborating implementation plans and action plans in order to successfully achieve the objectives of sustainable trade development strategy. To assume the prime responsibility for, and coordinate with ministries, branches and localities in, implementing a group of solutions in order to develop trade, improve quality and competitiveness of goods, accelerate investment in export goods production projects. import goods or substitutes, and improve the effectiveness of trade promotion activities of provinces and cities nationwide.

Giving better advice to the Government in formulating commodity trade strategies and strategies for international integration, negotiation and signing of bilateral, regional and multilateral trade agreements. Review Vietnam's trade policies for Sustainable Development Goals. There are flexible management solutions, timely remove difficulties and congestion in trade. Promote market forecasting, consumer demand, provide market information, find and expand markets. To coordinate with ministries, branches and localities in

promulgating technical measures, hygiene, plant quarantine, environmental standards for domestic goods and import and export, ensuring harmony between trade development. and environmental protection, consumer health protection. Annually, to assume the prime responsibility for, and coordinate with ministries, agencies and branches in, evaluating the implementation of the Trade Sustainable Development Strategy and proposing to the Government results, promptly supplementing and adjusting them to suit the reality. , in order to successfully achieve the goal of sustainable trade development in general, Bac Ninh province in particular.

(iii) With the People's Committee of Bac Ninh Province

Deploy plans, strategies for sustainable trade development in the province to all levels, sectors and business associations. Based on the general and specific policies of the central government, concretize them into the regulations of the Province in order to manage commercial activities which are not contrary to general regulations and suitable to the local practical situation. The provincial People's Committee needs to closely guide and inspect and supervise the implementation of the management agencies and enterprises seriously. At the same time, the strategy of sustainable trade development in the province is open, so it is necessary to review and adjust in each period to suit the socio-economic development situation of the province, the region and country.

(iv) With commercial enterprises in the area

Commercial enterprises in the province should formulate, enhance the role of Bac Ninh trade enterprises association in the process of forming goods supply chains, ensuring sustainable competitiveness for the enterprises. member. To well perform the role of associations and industry business representatives who have a voice to the Government, ministries and branches in time to solve difficulties and problems to create favorable conditions for enterprises to develop sustainably. Contribute ideas in formulating new relevant mechanisms and policies.

It is necessary to strengthen the organizational structure, operational models, market research and marketing, improve the effectiveness of trade promotion activities.

To build and pay attention to information and data channels on domestic and foreign markets, on goods and trade promotion, to promote cooperation with neighboring provinces, and professional associations in the region and above. world to enlist financial support, science and technology, business experience ...

Focusing on training human resources, raising qualifications, business skills and propaganda to raise awareness of environmental protection, stable and sustainable trade development.

In the process of creating the sustainability of the world, people have constantly created to find the truth of development. The idea of Sustainable Development is a revolutionary advance in the concept of development and civilization of mankind that has been attractive to nations in the direction of choosing a path of development. Sustainable development is becoming an inevitable global trend, a goal of countries in the world. In order to ensure the sustainable development of an economy, it requires sustainable development in all areas, of which the indispensable area of trade in countries in general and localities in particular. Sustainable trade development in Bac Ninh province plays a very important role for the sustainable development of the province's economy.

References

- i. *Advisory Committee on Official Statistics (2009), Good practice guidelines for the development and reporting of indicators. Wellington: Statistics New Zealand*
- ii. *Baker, Susan; Kousis, Maria, Richardson, Dick and Young, Stephen (1997): The Politics of Sustainable Developmen. Theory, Policy and Practice Within The European, Routledge, London and NewYork.*

- iii. Baumol W. and Oates (1998), *The theory of Environmental Policy*.
- iv. Bastiaan Zoeteman and Wouter Kersten (2008), *Stimulating Sustainable trade Aiming at a Joint government business approach addressing, paper Sustainable trade addressing NTCs*, Tiburg University.
- v. Bill Vorley, Dilys Roe, Steve Bass (2000), *Standards and Sustainable trade*, paper International institute for environment and development, London, April 2000.
- vi. Centre for Environment Education (2007). *Sustainable Development: An Introduction (Intership Series, Volume-I)*, India.
- vii. Cline, William (2004), “*The World trade policy and poverty*”, *International Institute of economics*, Washington.
- viii. Dasgupta S., Laplante B. and N. Mamingi N. (1999), *Trade policy Responses to environmental Performance in Developing Countries*, World Bank.
- ix. Fely David (2005), *Understanding and doing Research: a handbook for beginners*. NXB panorsma Printing Inc, 2005.
- x. Field B. & Olewiler N. (2005), *Environmental Economic*. McGraw-Hill Ryerson Higher Education.
- xi. Frans Crul (2013), *China and south Africa on their way to Sustainable trade relations*, Trade working paper, Trade law centre.
- xii. Ian Coxhead (2006), *International trade and the Natural Resource “curse” in Southeast Asia: does China’s growth threaten Regional Development*, University of Wisconsin.
- xiii. International Trade Centre (2007), *Competitiveness Report 2007*.
- xiv. International Trade Centre (2008), *Statistics Database 2008*.
- xv. IISD-UNEP (2002), *Environment and Trade- A Handbook*.
- xvi. Jccobs, P. and Sadler, B. (eds) (1989) *Sustainable Development and Environmental Assessment: Perspectives on Planning for a Common Future Canadian Environmental Assessment Research Council*, Quebec.
- xvii. John Blewitt (2008), *Understanding Sustainable Development*, Earth Scan, Sterling, VA.
- xviii. Khalid Saeed, *Social science and policy studies department* (1996), *Sustainable trade relations in Global economy*, Worcester polytechnic Institute, Worcester, MA 01.609, USA.
- xix. Mark Halle and Long Guogiang (2010), *Elements of sustainable trade strategy for China*, International Institute for Sustainable Development.
- xx. Perter P. Roger, Kazi F. Jalal, and John A. Boyd (2007), *An introduction to sustainable Development*, Earth Scan, Sterling, VA.
- xxi. Roberts, Robins (2000), *The Reality of Sustainable trade*. IIED London.
- xxii. Shawkat Alam (2007), *Sustainable Development and Free Trade: Institutional Approaches*,
- xxiii. Simon Bell và Stephen Morse (2008), *Sustainability Indicators: Measuring the Immeasurable?*, Sterling, VA.
- xxiv. Simon Dresner (2009), *The Principles of sustainability*, Earth Scan, Sterling, VA.
- xxv. Simon Kuznets (1995), *Economic Growth and Income Inequality*, *The American Economic Review*, Mar.1995 (Vol.45,NO.1), pp1-28 .
- xxvi. Soubotina (2005), *Không chỉ là tăng trưởng kinh tế, Nhập môn về phát triển bền vững. Nhà xuất bản văn hóa thông tin, Hà Nội*.
- xxvii. Strachan, Janet R.; Sell, Malena; Gueye, Moustapha Kamal (2010), *Trade, climate change and sustainable development: key issues for small states, least developed countries and vulnerable economies*,
- xxviii. *Sustainable Development in India* (2011), *Stocktaking in the run up to Rio +20*.
- xxix. Sven Hibig (2014), “*Yes to a sustainable trade policy – No to the Transatlantic trade and Investment partnership*”, BROT, *Für die welt*.
- xxx. Tietenberg, T. (2002), *Environmental and Natural Resources Economics*, Addison Wesley.

- xxxi. *Tran Chi Thien (2013), Viet Nam-South Korea economic co-operation: economic theories and practice, Statistical publishing house, January 2013.*
- xxxii. *UNCTAD (United Nation Confeence on trade and Developmen), Trade & Sustainable Developmen, Berlin, 1997.*
- xxxiii. *UNCTAD (United Nation Confeence on trade and Developmen), Sustainable Management: Climate-change Mitigation and Resource/Material Efficiency - What is Myth and what Reality?, Berlin, 26 Jan 2010.WCED, 1987.*
- xxxiv. *UNCTAD (2007), Sustainable trade of Arapaima gigas in Amazon region,United Nations Publication.*
- xxxv. *UNCTAD (2008), Staticstics Handbook 2008.*
- xxxvi. *UNEP (2004), Sustainable trade and Poverty Reduction, Integrated Assessment and planning.*
- xxxvii. *WCED (1987), Report of World Commission on Enviroment and Developmen: “Our common future”, Nairobi – Kenya.*
- xxxviii. *Zoltan Ban (2011), Sustainable trade: changing the eviroment the market operates in, through Standardized Global trade tariffs, Author House*

APPENDIX

Factors that are measured on a 5-point Likert scale from 1 are Strongly Disagree to 5 are Strongly Agree.

1. Sustainable trade development

a. Growth scale of Tradition

Business situation is increasingly favorable

The market provides input products for businesses very smoothly

Enterprises are satisfied with the amount of products they sell

Export turnover increased over the previous year

Import turnover increased over the previous year

b. Growth quality of Tradition

Efficiency of trade is increasingly favorable

Revenue is increasing

Fully meet the needs of using goods

Circulating goods are mainly raw products

Export goods are mainly raw products

c. Labor and income in the commercial sector

The number of employees in enterprises has increased over the years

The income of workers is always increasing

Enterprises always focus on improving skills and qualifications for employees

The rights of employees at the workplace are always focused

d. The level of trade friendliness with the environment

NVL mainly exploits from domestic natural resources

The current exploitation of natural resources has not been thoroughly dealt with

Need to invest in product processing technology

Enterprises always apply waste treatment measures

The propaganda for employees to raise environmental protection awareness is respected

2. Factors affecting sustainable trade development in Bac Ninh

a. International integration

The market of enterprises' products is expanded

Enterprises apply modern science and technology from import

Solving many jobs, raising income for laborers

There are many opportunities to provide these inputs

The risk of environmental pollution increases (Exploiting natural resources for production, importing outdated technology ...)

The competitive pressure of enterprises is bigger

No big impact on business activities of enterprises

b. Commercial institution

Environmental regulations and standards are high and difficult to meet

Environmental protection policy has not been paid attention

Insufficient support policies for enterprises (capital, interest rates, taxes ...)

The coordination between economic policy and environmental policy has not been taken seriously

The mechanism of management and supervision of implementation of import and export policies is still loose, sanctions are not strict

c. Natural condition

Favorable geographical location for goods trading and exchange activities

Mineral resources are abundant and diverse

The method of exploiting natural resources is not effective

Production inputs of raw materials are mainly imported from abroad

The input raw materials for product production of the establishments mainly exploit natural resources in the province

There is no measure to handle illegal natural resource exploitation

d. Human Resources

Human resources of businesses increased over the years

The level of human resources is limited

It is not difficult to recruit outsourced workers

All human resources work hard

Training for highly qualified human resources is always concerned

Lack of highly qualified human resources

e. Commercial infrastructure

Infrastructure has not guaranteed well for goods trading

Convenient transportation system for goods trading activities

Supermarkets, shopping malls, logistics have not been developed

Market scale needs to be expanded

The investment in construction of commercial infrastructure has not been given practical attention

f. Science and technology

Lack of machinery, equipment and environmentally friendly technology lines

Improved product quality thanks to science and technology

Mainly importing science and technology from abroad

Reduce the proportion of raw and semi-processed products

Limit pollution and environmental degradation

Improve labor productivity of businesses

Need to invest in improving science and technology capacity